

FEATURES OF THE ANDROID STUDIO SOFTWARE PACKAGE

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Abstract: This article reviews the capabilities of the Android Studio software package.

Keywords: Multimedia tools, programming technologies, Android studio, mobile application, programming languages.

The process of implementing personalized education with the help of multimedia tools requires the development and use of modern, multidisciplinary, subject-oriented multimedia educational tools. According to the possibilities of taking into account the individual characteristics of learners and helping to increase their interest (motivation), as well as according to the qualities of compatibility, interactivity, flexibility of various types of multimedia educational information, multimedia is useful and productive education. lim technology. Android (from the Greek andro - "man", suffix - "robot"; "humanoid robot") - smartphones, tablets, e-books, digital players, wristwatches, fitness bracelets, game consoles, laptops, netbooks, smartbooks, Google Glass glasses, televisions,

Originally this operating system Android Inc. was developed by, later acquired by Google. The operating system is based on the Linux kernel and the Java virtual machine developed by Google. Later, Google created the Open Handset Alliance (OHA) to support and further develop this platform.

The Android operating system allows the device to run Java applications controlled by libraries developed by Google. Android Native Development Kit allows you to work with libraries and application components written in C and other programming languages.

In the second quarter of 2014, Android was installed on 86% of smartphones sold worldwide, and in May 2017, Google announced that more than 2 billion Android devices had been activated in the entire history of Android.

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Development of data encryption software using multiple algorithms on Android devices and use in sms messenger

Almost daily, new details about the operation of the US National Security Agency's (NSA) PRISM electronic intelligence program have caused a predictable reaction in society. Citizens of the United States and other countries have begun to show great interest in various alternative search engines, social networks and other online services that provide increased levels of communication privacy and privacy for their users, in particular encryption, and both Apple and Google PRISM taking into account that he was found guilty of involvement in the program (at least

on the collection of metadata from Verizon Wireless operators), many mobile users were surprised to find ways to protect their smartphones and tablets from the excessive attention of special services. from prying eyes. Of course, everything is very complicated: switching to another website, renegotiating the contract with another provider and buying a new mobile device are not measures that allow you to hide from PRISM. To protect your personal data, for example, at home, experts recommend using fast data encryption on smartphones and tablets. This method means that before sending the data is first encrypted on the outgoing device and after sending ng will be encrypted on the receiving device. It sounds a bit like a spy. But in practice, operational encryption does not look so mysterious, works very efficiently and resembles simple mobile applications that allow data transfer bypassing PRISM-controlled servers. There are many software products that use operational encryption, although they are not very popular. Here's a small list of mobile apps and services that make your data and/or tablet more resistant to both PRISM and other equally obnoxious data-gathering surveillance systems. works very efficiently and is similar to regular mobile apps that allow data transfer bypassing PRISM-managed servers. There are many software products that use operational encryption, although they are not very popular. Here's a small list of mobile apps and services that make your data and/or tablet more resistant to both PRISM and other equally obnoxious data-gathering surveillance systems. works very efficiently and is similar to regular mobile apps that allow data transfer bypassing PRISM-managed servers. There are many software products

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Encrypt phone conversations RedPhone (for Android): Free, open source software that can encrypt phone calls. Of course, RedPhone is effective when installed on both (or all) mobile devices participating in the conversation. RedPhone works over Wi-Fi or mobile Internet, not over a telephone connection, so the mobile operator cannot access the metadata of the phone conversation. Silent Phone (for iOS and Android): Offers a fixed monthly fee, but unlike RedPhone, allows cross-platform calling. Silent Phone provides the user with a unique 10-digit number that can be used in parallel with the operator's normal number. For an additional fee, Silent Phone customers they can also use their numbers to call third-party subscribers, but in this case the encryption of the conversation will be one-way. ChatSecure (for iOS) encrypts data transmitted by chat participants, works with Google Chat and Jabber (* you can download Jabber), and can also be used for cross-platform data transfer. TextSecure (for Android) was developed by the authors of RedPhone and can be used as a replacement for the standard Android program for sending SMS / MMS messages. To protect data, TextSecure must also be installed on all mobile devices participating in the correspondence. It should also be noted that

Ekboo (for BlackBerry) is a BlackBerry BBM encryption plugin with a unique TextBomb feature that allows you to send text messages that are automatically deleted after a user-defined time. Mobile data encryption Orweb (for Android) - the program was created by experts of the Guardian project and recommended for use by the electronic border fund. Orweb is a way to bypass network restrictions and encrypt a user's network activity using Tor software. In other words, Orweb allows you to hide which device is used for web surfing, manage cookies and block Flash. In addition, Orweb does not store any browsing history. To work more effectively with Orweb, its developers recommend using Orbot. Onion Browser (for iOS): For just \$1, an iOS user can access the Tor network and hide their IP address and web activity. Email Encryption Locked (for iOS, Android and other operating systems) can be downloaded and installed as a simple application on any iOS or Android device, where it works as a plug-in to a standard web browser. Enlocked allows you to send and receive encrypted emails in Gmail, Yahoo, AOL and Outlook. it also gives you the option to hide your IP address and web activity. Email Encryption Locked (for iOS, Android and

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Enlocked is distributed free of charge, the only condition for using the program is that it must be installed on the mobile devices of all participants in the correspondence. X-Telecom Secure Mobile software and server solution was developed by an international team of cryptography and programming experts. Our leading experts regularly participate in international exhibitions, conferences and symposia on cryptography, such as CRYPTO and CHES, which are attended by leading engineers and scientists from more than 30 countries. Several different crypto-algorithms are used to encrypt the data on our crypto phones, including the cascade encryption mechanism, the main ones being AES and Twofish, other algorithms and protocols are available for auxiliary and reliable user authentication. Our voice call and file transfer system has an encryption feature called Perfect-forward-privacy. This means that the encryption keys for each sent conversation or file are unique and are destroyed when the session ends. Features of X-Telecom crypto phone X-Telecom crypto phone uses AES encryption algorithm with 256-bit key. In addition, all data blocks encrypted with the AES-256 algorithm are additionally encrypted by X-Telecom cryptophones with the TwoFish algorithm, which is also invulnerable to hacking. This is done to ensure the reliability of the password. For example, The AES-128 encryption algorithm is used in US government agencies to encrypt information with the SECRET stamp, and the AES-256 encryption algorithm is used for TOP SECRET documents. That is, the use of a single AES-256 encryption algorithm makes the data transmitted through our cryptophones safe and provides additional 100% protection of the Twofish algorithm and auxiliary algorithms. The encryption keys of the conversation session are randomly generated in the cryptophones themselves, and the system automatically destroys them after the end of the conversation, and then new keys are generated randomly, that is, no one knows the keys. The use of a single AES-256 encryption algorithm makes the data transmitted through our cryptophones

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Operation scheme of the cryptophone X-Telecom cryptophones require Internet connection via WI-FI or any cellular operator by installing a SIM card in the phone. Call security SIP TLS protocol is used for signaling (for example, about the start of a call). The voice channel is secured with a 256-bit AES / Twofish symmetric cipher, which is extracted using ZRTP. The ICE protocol decides which method to use to connect subscribers: if the connection goes through STUN, then P2P with ZRTP is used, if the connection does not go through a direct proxy, then TURN is used with ZRTP. The ZRTP protocol is used for key assignment. ZRTP generates a unique encryption key for each conversation. Keys are generated on phones and transmitted securely to another subscriber using the Diffie-Hellman protocol. ZRTP is reliably protected against a so-called "man-in-the-middle" attack using a SAS hash value. SAS is a short text string that is verbally confirmed by both parties at the start of the conversation. After such a check, both parties can be sure that there is no hacker in their midst. Text messages work like PGP - end-to-end encryption is used. An AES-256 mod GCM cipher type that guarantees message validity and authenticity at the same time. Text messages are delivered using the SIP TLS protocol. Offline messages and read receipt messages are also supported. The app also provides another layer of security for messaging.

Android Studio is an integrated development environment for working with the Android platform, which was announced at the Google I/O conference on May 16, 2013.

This IDE has been freely available since version 0.1 released in May 2013 and then went into beta testing with version 0.8 released in June 2014. The first stable version 1.0 was released in December 2014, while support for the Android Ertasolja Hedaz (ADT) plugin for esah has ended.

Based on JetBrains' IntelliJ IDEA, Android Studio is the official Android app development tool. This development environment is available for Windows, macOS and GNU/Linux. On May 17, 2017, at the annual Google I/O conference, Google announced support for Kotlin, the language used in Android Studio, as the official programming language for the Android platform in addition to Java and C++. Android Features New features come with every new version of Android Studio. The following functions are currently available. Advanced layout editor: WYSIWYG, ability to work with UI components using Drag-and-Drop, layout preview function in multiple screen configurations. Gradle-based application structure. Different types of structures and several . generating apk files Processing the code. A static code analyzer (Lint) that allows you to find performance issues, version incompatibilities, and more. Built-in ProGuard and application signing utility. Android Basic Layout and Component Templates. App development support for Android Wear and Android TV .Built-in support for Google Cloud Platform, including integration with Google Cloud Messaging and App Engine services. Android Studio 2.1 supports the Android N Preview SDK, App development support for Android Wear and Android TV .Built-in support for Google Cloud Platform, including integration with Google Cloud Messaging and App Engine services. Android Studio 2.1 supports the Android N Preview SDK, App development support for Android Wear and Android TV .Built-in support for Google Cloud Platform, including integration with Google Cloud Messaging and App Engine services. Android Studio 2.1 supports the Android N Preview SDK,

Among the stages of development that involve the implementation of applications in Android Studio, we find four stages. The first is environment settings; In this phase, the development environment is set up and configured. In addition, the connection to the elements on which the application can be installed is established and Android virtual devices (AVDS) are created. The second phase covers the following: Project configuration and development; During this, the configuration of the project and its development are carried out. We are talking about creating modules that contain resources for the program and source code. The third phase includes debugging, debugging, and building the program; At this point, the project can be installed and run on an emulator or Android device.) has been installed into a debuggable .apk package(s). A build system based on Gradle is used.

It provides flexibility, custom build options, and dependency resolution. If another IDE is used, the project can be developed using Gradle and in turn

installed on the device using OTB. Then, the application control messages are debugged by the Android logging tool (Logcat) along with the IntelliJ idea. It is also possible to use the compatible JDWP debugger, adding the debugging and logging tools provided with the Android SDK. Finally, the Android SDK testing tools are used to test the application.

We already know the steps and development of Android app development. Referring to the module base, each project contains one or more modules with source code files and resource files. Which types include; Android application modules, library modules, test modules and App Engine modules. By default, Android Studio displays project files in the Android Project view. At this point, the modules appear organized to provide quick access to the underlying source code files. When compiling files, they appear under the top-level Scripts Gradle. At Studio Android, we already understand that Gradle is used as the basis of the application development system.

This build system works as a tool built into the Android Studio menu and, in turn, serves as an independent launch from the command line.

So if your server is hacked and someone watches your message, they won't be able to read it because the message is encrypted with your SAS code. File transfer When transferring files (audio recordings, photos and videos), RFC 5245 (ICE, NAT traversal mechanism) and RFC 5766 (TURN helpers for NAT traversal or, in the worst case, TURN server is used as an intermediary (replacement)) is used - in this case it is a p2p client-server-client communication). First, information about existing IP addresses is collected, as well as information about IP addresses configured on the network interfaces of subscribers who can receive network traffic. ICE Protocol Received Information About Available IPs aggregates the data and creates the most convenient routes to these IP addresses. Packet transmission uses "Pseudo TCP" technology, which is used to send packets via UDP. After the data is transferred, the integrity of the file and the recipient is checked, thus ensuring that the file is transferred completely and as intended.

Cryptophone works stably on any communication network, even with a weak signal Voice and message encryption Reliable participant verification procedure Full protection to prevent attackers and malicious code from entering Our encrypted VoIP networks design allows you to record phone calls and does not allow recording, so all your conversations remain anonymous. About the draft law, which should prohibit the use of mobile devices without certificates by the authorities, because, according to the author of the law, they threaten

national security. Still! If American special services find out what our deputies are talking about, they will never destroy our country. would have understood that they would not lub! After all, if we somehow develop and are elected, then what will happen to us if worthy people come to the State Duma? Last time I looked at different alternatives to the usual iPhone replacements, but they all have one thing in common - you have to give up your usual phone and switch to a new device or carry a second one with you, especially for confidential conversations. Is it convenient? but they all have one thing in common - you need to give up your usual phone and switch to a new device or carry a second one with you, especially for confidential conversations. Is it convenient? but they all have one thing in common - you need to give up your usual phone and switch to a new device or carry a second one with you, especially for confidential conversations. Is it convenient?

That's why I suggested at the end of the last entry and that no one will voluntarily give up their Vertu and iPhones, and here a day ago journalists asked me a question - have I heard about Russian headsets for mobile devices that encrypt voice traffic that starts immediately from the headset? ..

I didn't hear it, but I started digging. Basically, the brief results of my digging (no claim to completeness). So, if we reject the option of providing privacy in the phone itself (very dependent on the mobile OS and platform version) and the use of special phone hardware (inconvenient), then we have two options to solve the problem: encryption at the "layer", which is an intermediate crypto-module between the encryption headset and the phone itself. Journalists talked to me about the first option, while mentioning ruselektronika, which was supposed to fill the Russian market with specialized headphones with internal encryption. But because I didn't look, I did not find an enterprise that already produces such devices. I thought that there might be an Octava design bureau in Tula, which specializes in the production of headsets for security forces, special services, the Ministry of Emergency Situations, etc., but I did not find anything related to cryptography from them. A statement was made by "Ruselectronics" about the release of crypto modules for YotaPhone, but it has little to do with headphones - it is a clear dependence on the device platform. In principle, modern headsets such as Plantronics or Jabra encrypt the sound from the microphone to the computer (or any device connected to the headset) using the 128-bit E0 algorithm included in the Bluetooth protocol.

Rather, it is a solution to protect the wireless connection from the headset to the computer or phone, which can be up to 100-120 meters between them. It

is logical to assume that such a channel in an unprotected version is easily found and therefore requires protection.

I have not found any other cryptographic data protection tools built into the headset. But I found several applications of the second solution I mentioned. For example, TopSec Mobile from Rode-Schwartz. It is a hardware device independent of the phone or computer model it is connected to. Negotiations are carried out through TopSec Mobile itself, through a headset delivered to the mouth during a call or connected to a cryptomodule. The only drawback of this approach is the presence of a special call management server between subscribers registered on the server. But this is a necessary condition for creating distributed interaction systems. The second device I found is the GUARD Bluetooth scrambler from local company LOGOS. An early shovel device. There is no design. The headset is firmly "stitched" to the device and can only be replaced with a device. But the protection of negotiations is guaranteed - the device is connected to a transmitter via Bluetooth - a computer or a phone (not a word is said about the protection of the Bluetooth channel using E0). The device has not been tested, but its review can be found on the net. In comparison with the same TopSec Mobile, the appearance of "GUARD Bluetooth" is based on local and western cryptographic data protection tools (and for appearance, ease of use, and functionality). But for the operation of this device, an external server is not required - it can work "point-to-point". The headset is firmly "stitched" to the device and can only be replaced with a device. But the protection of negotiations is guaranteed - the device is connected to a transmitter via Bluetooth - a computer or a phone (not a word is said about the protection of the Bluetooth channel using E0). The device has not been tested, but its review can be found on the net. In comparison with the same TopSec Mobile, the appearance of "GUARD Bluetooth" is based on local and western cryptographic data protection tools (and for appearance, ease of use, and functionality). But for the operation of this device, an external server is

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The last solution I want to look at is IndependenceKey, which aims to protect various types of interactions between users. Types of protected communications include voice communications. However, this device is an intermediate option between a standalone cryptomodule and security software. In particular, the headset is connected to the IndependenceKey module, from which the encrypted sound in the module is transmitted, but then it goes to the software installed on the personal computer, where the IndependenceKey is installed on the USB connector. Connecting it to the phone will be problematic. These are the solutions. True, none of them are certified and are unlikely to be. Probably "Ruselektronika"

Data encryption tools have been around for a long time, but they all cost too much or require users to have extensive encryption knowledge. A group of

free and open-source advocates known as Open Whisper Systems hopes to right this injustice with a new Signal app. Signal claims to be the first iOS application designed to provide a simple and effective method of encryption for free. It should be noted that Open Whisper Systems has a lot of experience in this regard. Open Whisper Systems is known to many users as the developer of RedPhone and TextSecure Android apps for encrypting calls and messages, respectively. And now they decided to prove themselves in the iOS ecosystem. Signal uses the well-proven ZRTP cryptographic protocol and 128-bit AES to encrypt phone conversations. In theory, this protection is insufficient to withstand all attacks known to date, organized by anyone from kiddie script hackers to NSA experts. Even though the signal uses end-to-end encryption, the conversation itself looks familiar.

The application uses the user's phone number to work, no additional identifiers are required. Basically, Signal is a VoIP system.

The application allows you to establish an encrypted voice communication channel between end users over IP networks, so it uses non-cellular networks and the tariff plan relies on minutes and cellular or Wi-Fi networks. The only indication that a phone conversation between two users of Signal is encrypted and immune to man-in-the-middle attacks is the randomly generated pairs of words exchanged between the parties. To authenticate, the user must say these words aloud to the interlocutor on the other end of the line. The technology behind the Signal IP telephony service is not new. Moxie Marlinspike, renowned computer security expert and co-founder of Open Whisper Systems, said 4 years ago has countered the lack of encryption on smartphones with the Redphone VoIP system for Android. RedPhone, like Signal, uses the ZRTP protocol, one of whose developers is Philip Zimmerman, the creator of the cult encryption program PGP. Mr. Zimmerman also developed his own ZRTP software for his startup Silent Circle (hello), which sells call and message encryption software for iPhone and Android. However, unlike Open Whisper's systems, Silent Circles' customers are mostly corporate users who pay companies \$20 per month for using the proprietary Silent Circles software. Another advantage of the Open Whisper Systems solution is that Signal users can securely call Redphone users. can carry out tasks. All friends who use Redphone will be displayed in the Signal user's contact list. It's important to note that Signal benefits not only from Redphone's user database, but also from Redphone's physical infrastructure - a worldwide network of servers to route local calls to reduce latency.

In order to reassure users, the development team emphasized that Signal does not leave metadata, call logs are not stored on the company's servers

All encryption is done locally, on the smartphone itself. Signal offers the same services as Silent Circle but is completely free, making it the first free call encryption software of its kind. It's also worth noting that Signal is open source. The Signal iOS source code is published on Github. The application is still under development and the company invites all interested parties to check its reliability. It was also reported this summer that the program may support message encryption. Rather than going commercial, Open Whisper Systems has chosen to be independent and is funded by donations and government grants. It is worth noting that the well-known anonymous network Tor

Like every new program that supports encryption, Signal has not yet been tested for bugs, so do not fully trust the program until it has been thoroughly reviewed by various independent security experts. Moxie Marlinspike acknowledges that there are always unseen threats, such as vulnerabilities in iPhone software that allow attackers to eavesdrop on conversations. Alarm software can be downloaded for free from the application store CELLCRYPT SECUREGSM KRYPTOGIK 5PRO SOFTWARE SECURE VOICE FONECRYPT Gold lock COMPUMATICA GSM SMS encryption EPILOG Unfortunately, there is one problem - the legislation of the Russian Federation prohibits the use of encryption algorithms when exchanging voice data.

According to the Law "On Communications", all mobile operators in the territory of the Russian Federation are obliged to provide access to negotiations for any subscriber in the presence of relevant decisions of the prosecutor or judge. Therefore, your innocent conversations about girls and complaints about your mother-in-law in encrypted form will immediately attract the attention of security personnel. Perhaps after some time pative will visit, and the people who leave it will politely ask to never use programs to encrypt voice communications. Kreml777 Kreml777 2010-06-07T10: 29: 48Z 2010-06-07T10: 29: 48Z Encryption of conversations by mobile phone.

Encrypting conversations on a cell phone: how to protect yourself from eavesdropping Practice shows that not only can the computer of a "suspect" be hacked - the crypto protection of GSM cellular networks also does not help to protect your communication 100% from interception and eavesdropping (although although it is much more difficult to do). How to protect confidential information from prying eyes and ears? You can view sent text messages and mail messages, record conversations in completely different ways, let's look at

the main ones. The first and most common of them is the "error" in the subscriber's room. The necessary devices can be found on the Internet by a corresponding request on Yandex. The irony is that anyone can buy a bug. A device with a built-in SIM card allows you to listen to copies of the "victim" during phone conversations in the installed room. As you understand, there is no way to protect yourself from such "hacking" with any software - it's enough to turn on paranoia and search buildings or even go outside before an important call. A very popular method of espionage is a "Trojan horse" - a smartphone presented to the "victim" with the "back door" wide open. allows you to listen to copies. As you understand, there is no way to protect yourself from such "hacking" with any software - it's enough to turn on paranoia and search buildings or even go outside before an important call. A very popular method of espionage is a "Trojan horse" - a smartphone presented to the "victim" with the "back door" wide open. allows you to listen to copies. As you understand, there is no way to protect yourself from such "hacking" with any software - it's enough to turn on paranoia and search buildings or even go outside before an important call. A very popular method of espionage is a "Trojan horse" - a smartphone presented to the "victim" with the "back door" wide open.

Modern smartphones offer a variety of tools to record all conversations and text messages. At the same time, spyware is easily hidden in the system - it is unlikely that an inexperienced user will immediately know that it is listening. Phones have become a real find for such "operations" Apple iPhone - the device allows you to record everything that happened and remotely download the archive through built-in services. A godsend for industrial espionage. Alternatively, hackers can get hold of your favorite mobile phone and secretly install anti-spyware. Therefore, advice: do not believe such friendly "gifts" and if your car is a Mercedes-Benz of the latest model

Then there are more sophisticated ways to secretly listen to your phone, which is only possible when your secret communication costs a lot of money. We are talking about specialized mobile stations with antennas and computers, such as a GSM Passive Cellular Interceptor. They scan the frequency bands in which mobile phones operate, intercept and decode the conversation. Such devices do not attract the attention of mobile operators or touch the subscriber. Of the minuses - a very high price and the need to be at a distance of no more than three meters from the listener. Otherwise, the device will not be able to maintain the desired frequency correctly. Finally, government officials can listen to your conversations with the permission of the prosecutor / court - especially if

Here, everything is done according to the law - the court or a high-ranking official gives permission to restrict the communication secret of a subscriber suspected of illegal behavior. There is only one way to protect yourself from such interference in your private life - not to break the law. Alternatively, attackers can find a light worker of the operator company and pay him to listen to conversations that have already been opened through his keys. Phone encryption programs can protect against such mobile devices.

To use software encryption, you need a modern smartphone, and the more powerful it is, the better - real-time encryption using long keys requires a lot of system resources, so the device is under high load will have to work. Obviously, ordinary mobile phones with Java-based applications cannot cope with the intensive computing flow. CELLCRYPT The software list is opened by one of the most popular payment software, originally from Britain called Cellcrypt Mobile. A program with a good interface should be installed on both phones with which you will talk. In this case, the exchange of encrypted data takes place through the CSD channel, which means that you call from a modem to a modem.

To encrypt the signal, Cellcrypt uses a 256-bit key from the AES algorithm and a corresponding integrity check. The developer promises very reliable, clear voice communication without interference and loss of fragments - even the military can use Cellcrypt Mobile.

The program has passed compatibility tests with cellular networks, received FIPS 140-2 security certification in the United States, and is available for Nokia Symbian-based smartphones and advanced mobile phones from Canada's RIM Blackberry. As a nice addition, the latest version Cellcrypt Mobile has learned to make secure calls via satellite using the same Nokia and BlackBerry smartphones. For such a call, only a broadband terminal with a satellite connection is needed. SECUREGSM The very expensive SecureGSM software is designed for communication with mobile phones running the Microsoft Windows Mobile operating system - the developer's portfolio includes touch and an includes versions for devices with conventional displays. The program provides effective two-way protection against secret telephone conversations and sending encrypted text messages over the CSD data channel on cellular networks, wiretapping and message eavesdropping.

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